

Synthesis and stability studies in physiological-like conditions of a new compound of copper(II) with mixed ligands

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In order to obtain new potential antioxidants with molecular mass lower than those of the metal-proteins, a new copper(II) compound with mixed ligands, L-histidine and urea was synthesised. The compounds containing only one of the two mentioned ligands, Cu-urea and Cu-L-histidine was also synthesised as intermediates in the synthesis of the compound with mixed ligands or for comparative purposes. The spectral analysis indicates an axial symmetry of the Cu^{II} ions in the compound with mixed ligands. Stability studies, in time and in different pH-conditions, were carried out by absorption electronic spectroscopy; the results revealed satisfactory stability in time, at the pH of the physiologic serum of the compounds with mixed ligands; the compound is also stable in aqueous solutions at pH 7.2–5.5. The study of compatibility with physiological mediums indicates that the compound displays significant lypophilic character.

Copper metal-proteins are involved in various biological functions such are electron transfer, oxygen transport or substrate oxidation. Modelling of the metal-binding sites of the metal-proteins implies reproducibility of the reactivity of the protein active sites and also lower molecular weight. In metal activated enzymes, histidyl residues are known to be important metal binding sites¹. The role of imidazole-containing ligands, with respect to copper(II) coordination in solution, has been widely investigated, also when the *N*-terminal amino group of the peptide chain is not available for coordination², in such cases, the imidazole group may assume the important role of anchor site for copper(II).

Cardiac dysfunction has been largely attributed to the effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Inhibitors, antioxidants, ROS scavengers have been shown to reduce the severity of the heart injury during the post-ischaemia reperfusion but the cytotoxicity, the pro-oxidant activity and the high molecular weight limit the application of these compounds as cardioprotective agents³.

Some copper proteins also exert cardioprotective effects⁴. However, as proteins, some difficulties of their pharmacological formulation and administration may occur. A recent study⁵ revealed novel cardiac protective effects of urea. Urea is the most common nitrogen-containing end-product of protein catabolism and its synthesis is involved in the regulation of the chronic acid-base disturbances⁶. Urea also stimulates gene transcription and expression⁷ and it has an antioxidant effect, protecting brain, liver and heart from

peroxidation of lipids.

We intended to prepare potential antioxidants with the following pre-established characteristics : reproducibility of the active sites of some metal-proteins with proven antioxidant properties, significantly lower molecular weight, compatibility with and stability in physiological mediums. We report here the synthesis, characterization and the results of the stability and lypophilicity studies of a new copper(II) complex with mixed ligands, L-histidine and urea. The compounds containing only one of the two mentioned categories of the ligands (Cu-urea and Cu-L-histidine) were also synthesised, as intermediates in the synthesis of the compound with mixed ligands or for comparative purposes.

Results and discussion

Physical data of the synthesised complexes are presented in Table 1.

IR spectrum of the complex with mixed ligands was interpreted having as reference the assignments of the observed frequencies of urea and histidine. The data suggest that in [Cu(urea)₂Cl₂], coordination occurs both through nitrogen

Table 1. Physical data of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	Yield %	μ_{eff} B.M.	M.p. K	$\Lambda_M \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
[Cu(urea) ₂ Cl ₂]	Green	76	1.82	437.5	1.74
[Cu(His) ₂]Cl ₂	Blue	70	1.85	547.0	54.25
[Cu(His)(urea) ₂]Cl	Blue	67	1.87	659.0	87.02

and oxygen atoms.

The IR spectra clearly show the implication of urea in the coordination at the metallic centre in the case of the compound with mixed ligands. The assignments of the most significant IR bands are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Assignments of the most significant IR bands (cm^{-1})

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{CO}} + \nu_{\text{NH}_2}$	$\nu_{\text{COO}^{-1} \text{ as}} + \nu_{\text{NH}_2}$	$\nu_{\text{COO}^{-s}}$
Urea	3443			
	3346			
	3259	1680		
	3461			
[Cu(urea) ₂ Cl ₂]	3391			
	3355	1638		
	3231			
L-His	3150		1632	1321
	2950		1570	1250
[Cu(His) ₂ Cl ₂]	3120		1600	1347
	3095		1470	1240
[Cu(His)(urea) ₂]Cl	3390		1610	
	3350		1478	1380
	3125	1625	1340	1275
	2850			

The compound [Cu(urea)₂Cl₂] displays an intense RPE signal, with anisotropy of the g factor ($g_{\parallel} : g_x = 22428$; $g_{\perp} : g_y = 22025$, $g_z = 20443$), suggesting an octahedral symmetry with rhombic distortion around the metal ions. The large bands with maxima at 11300, 12500 and 13800 cm^{-1} , are assigned to the transitions $z^2 \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$ (${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$), $xy \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$ (${}^2A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$) and $xz, yz \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$ (${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$) respectively. The value of the λ parameter ($g_{\parallel} = 2 - (8\lambda/\Delta E_{xy})$, where ΔE_{xy} is the energy of the transition $xy \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$) is $\lambda = -380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ratio λ/λ_0 of 0.45 ($\lambda_0 = -828 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) corresponds to an accentuated covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds. The value 1.98 of the G ratio, $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$ is lower than 4, indicating a strong field of ligands around copper ions and strong spin-spin interactions.

Compound [Cu(His)₂]Cl₂ has an isotropic RPE spectrum, with $g_i = 2.0945$. This value, close to 2, is a typical for a tetrahedral symmetry, with a xy ground state. The large band observed in the electronic spectrum by diffuse reflectance corresponds to three maxima at 10752 (transition $xz, yz \rightarrow xy$), 13500 (transition $z^2 \rightarrow xy$) and 15500 cm^{-1} (transition $x^2 - y^2 \rightarrow xy$). The value 1.96 of the G ratio, calculated as shown above, indicates a strong field of ligands

around copper ions and strong spin-spin interactions.

The RPE spectrum of [Cu(His)(urea)₂]Cl displays an axial symmetry, with the values of the g factor of $g_{\parallel} = 2.1520$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.0774$, the ground state orbital being $x^2 - y^2$. The bands in the diffuse reflectance electronic spectrum, very intense and large, correspond to three maxima at 10200 ($z^2 \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$), 13150 ($xy \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$) and 14900 cm^{-1} ($xy, yz \rightarrow x^2 - y^2$). The rather low value of the λ parameter (-249 cm^{-1} , $\lambda/\lambda_0 = 0.30$) reveals a strong covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds.

Stability studies, in time and in different pH-conditions, were carried out by absorption electronic spectroscopy in $10^{-3} M$ aqueous solutions^{9,10} and the results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Absorbance electronic spectra of the compound [Cu(His)₂]Cl₂. (a) At pH 7.2, in time: (1) 0, (2) 2, (3) 4 h. (b) At different pHs: (1) 7.2, (2) 6.2, (3) 5.5, (4) 4.5.

The compatibility with physiological mediums was investigated by thin layers chromatography of the compounds in $10^{-3} M$ aqueous solutions. The stationary phase was silica gel chemically bonded (Nano-Sil NH₂/UV₂₄₅) and the mobile phase was a 1 : 1 mixture of water and methanol; the visualization was improved in UV-light. The R_f values indicate that the compounds display significant lipophilic character; the values (mm) are as follows: [Cu(urea)₂]Cl₂, 41; [Cu(His)₂]Cl₂, 32; [Cu(His)(urea)₂]Cl, 26.

The results indicate stability in and compatibility with the physiological medium, comparable with those of other studied compounds¹¹ and justify the further investigation of the antioxidant activity of these compounds.

Fig. 2. Absorbance electronic spectra of the compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{His})(\text{urea})_2]\text{Cl}$. (a) At pH 7.2, in time : (1) 0, (2) 2, (3) 4 h. (b) At different pHs : (1) 7.2, (2) 6.2, (3) 5.5, (4) 4.5.

Experimental

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, urea, L-histidine were of A.R. grade and were used as such.

M.ps. were measured using a SMP-3 apparatus. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded with a BIORAD FTIR 135 spectrophotometer, diffuse reflectance spectra with MgO standard, on a VSU2-P-Zeiss Jena spectrophotometer, absorption electronic spectra on a Jasco V 530 spectrophotometer, in physiological serum (aq. NaCl, 0.9%), in non-modified and modified pH conditions and ESR spectra on an ART 5 spectrometer at room temperature. The pH was adjusted with 0.1 N HCl and measured with a Mettler 335 apparatus. The molar conductivity was measured in $10^{-1}M$ aq. solutions on a Consort C533 apparatus. Magnetic moment was determined by the Faraday method. The lipophylicity was evaluated by two dimensional chro-matography.

Syntheses :

The Cu-urea intermediary was prepared by adding dropwise, on ice, a cold a isopropyl alcohol solution of copper(II) chloride to an aqueous urea solution (in minimum of water) (in 4 : 1 molar ratio urea : CuCl_2 and 50 : 1 volumes ratio isopropyl alcohol : H_2O). The mixture was stirred on ice during 30 min. The resulting water-soluble bluish green solid was washed with isopropyl alcohol and dried¹². The elemental analysis indicates that its composition is $\text{Cu}(\text{urea})_2\text{Cl}_2$.

The preparation of the Cu-histidine complex was realized by adapting a method described in literature for the compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{His})_2](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ¹³. A cold ethanolic solution of copper(II) chloride was added, dropwise, on ice, to an aqueous solution of L-histidine (in the 2 : 1 molar ratio L-histidine : CuCl_2). The resulting deep blue, water-soluble complex was washed with isopropyl alcohol and dried. The elemental analysis indicates the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{His})_2\text{Cl}_2$.

The Cu-histidine-urea complex was prepared from a 1 : 1 mixture of aqueous solutions of Cu-urea complex and L-histidine, previously stirred at 50° for ~1 h. Addition of a large amount of ethanol to this mixture, cooled on ice, produced a greenish blue microcrystalline, water-soluble compound, whose elemental analysis indicated a $[\text{Cu}(\text{His})(\text{urea})_2]\text{Cl}$ composition.

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